

Evolution in Security and Privacy for 6G Networks: AI Perspectives and Key Enablers

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Abstract—Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a key enabler of intelligent management, optimization, and security in the evolution of sixth-generation (6G) networks. Although AI can significantly enhance security and privacy, it also introduces new vulnerabilities and challenges related to sustainability, regulation, and ethics. This paper presents an interdisciplinary review of AI-driven security and privacy mechanisms for 6G, and analyzes emerging threats, countermeasures, and architectural enablers for secure and privacy-aware services. It further discusses the sustainability and legal implications of AI-based solutions and identifies key research directions for trustworthy AI-powered 6G ecosystems. Going beyond a state-of-the-art (SoTA) survey, this paper includes an experimental feasibility analysis of Large Language Model (LLM)-based intrusion detection for future networks, aligned with recent advances in Generative AI (GAI).

Keywords—6G, AI, Security and Privacy, LLM, Legal and Ethical Compliance

I. INTRODUCTION

As fifth-generation (5G) networks become integral to modern wireless communication, efforts are underway to develop and standardize 6G networks. 6G is expected to deliver transformative capabilities, including holographic communication, collaborative robotics, and ultra-reliable low-latency services. Among its enabling technologies, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is central to realizing smart 6G networks and services. With vast data from diverse applications and advancements in computing and learning platforms, AI is poised to achieve levels of superintelligence beyond the reach of traditional optimization methods [1]. However, security remains a major challenge, especially in light of emerging regulations such as the EU AI Act and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Robust security is vital as 6G is deeply integrated with critical sectors such as healthcare, transportation, and energy. Privacy is also a growing concern, particularly for sensitive applications, such as healthcare [2]. Consequently, identifying the key enablers of security and privacy in 6G is essential to guide future research.

AI and machine learning (ML) are transforming various industries, including telecommunications. In 6G, AI/ML is being explored to enhance data security and to enable smart services. For instance, Federated Learning (FL) allows decentralized model training on mobile devices without centralized data collection, thereby improving data privacy and allowing privacy-enhancing techniques such as differential privacy and secure aggregation [3]. Additionally, AI-enhanced

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) and Explainable AI (XAI) are emerging as key enablers of secure 6G networks. However, AI/ML-driven security also introduces new threats, such as model poisoning and vulnerabilities at the network edge [4]. The implementation of AI for 6G security must also address broader challenges, such as sustainability [5] and AI ethics [6]. Specifically, security solutions should minimize energy consumption and optimize efficiency while ensuring that AI methods are trustworthy, safe, and comply with relevant legal standards.

This study investigates the SoTA in addressing 6G security challenges from an AI perspective. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews AI/ML-based security mechanisms for 6G. Section III examines emerging AI-driven threats and corresponding countermeasures. Section IV explores the sustainability aspects. Section V discusses key legal and ethical considerations. Section VI presents a feasibility study on the use of LLMs in modern IDS. Finally, Section VII concludes the study.

II. AI AND ML-DRIVEN SECURITY AND PRIVACY MECHANISMS IN 6G

Fig. 1: AI and ML-Driven Security Mechanisms on 6G Stack

AI and its subclass ML are expected to play key roles in securing the 6G architecture and integrated use cases. In this dimension, AI-enhanced IDS, FL, and XAI are highlighted as critical advancements, as shown in Fig. 1. In this vein, the following section describes how advances in these technologies will impact security and privacy in future 6G networks.

A. AI-Enhanced Network Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS)

B5G/6G applications will be dynamic and diverse, ranging from massive IoT deployments to advanced scenarios such as Industry 5.0. The increasing complexity and evolving nature of threats in 6G require advanced IDS with adaptive capabilities. Although AI/ML-driven IDS is foundational, 6G solutions must go beyond traditional anomaly detection by incorporating innovative adaptive techniques. In particular, continual or lifelong learning approaches show promise in addressing previously unseen threats [7]. GAI techniques, such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and transformer-based models, including LLMs, can further enhance the adaptability and performance of IDS [8] (Section VI further investigates the feasibility of using LLMs in IDS). These AI-enhanced IDSs must also contend with emerging challenges from quantum computing, distributed edge environments, and sophisticated attacks, such as GAI-based model poisoning.

B. Federated Learning (FL)

Intelligent networks are central to 6G, enabling autonomous and adaptive processing. FL is a key enabler, particularly for AI-as-a-Service (AIaaS) in 6G applications [9]. Use cases such as healthcare, smart cities, and Industry 5.0 involve extensive data collection, making centralized ML approaches highly vulnerable to privacy breaches, with potentially severe financial and reputational consequences. FL mitigates these risks by training models locally on user devices (e.g., smartphones and wearables) and transmitting only model updates to a central server for aggregation [10]. This decentralized approach is aligned with 6G requirements. To further support distributed intelligence, Distributed Federated Learning (DFL) [11] eliminates the centralized coordinator by allowing direct communication among clients [9], [12], improving robustness and security by removing single points of failure. DFL also improves power efficiency and connectivity, which are key challenges in earlier FL implementations. However, FL and DFL face persistent challenges, including eavesdropping, transparency issues, model poisoning, and memorization attacks [10]. To address these evolving threats, the integration of FL with continuous learning [7] offers a promising solution that enhances adaptability and resilience in B5G/6G environments. Moreover, privacy, robustness, and communication/computation efficiency may emerge as contradictory requirements for FL. For instance, secure aggregation may be employed for privacy enhancement in FL, but it also introduces additional cryptographic operations and message exchanges compared to standard aggregation.

C. Explainable AI (XAI)

Unlike 5G, which incorporates AI primarily at the application level, 6G is expected to integrate AI across all network layers, from intelligent sensing and data mining to smart

control and applications [13]. This deep integration is expected to improve the robustness, efficiency, and resource allocation throughout the 6G architecture [12]. However, reliance on AI-driven real-time decision-making in mission-critical tasks (e.g., autonomous driving and dynamic resource management) raises concerns regarding trust and accountability. The complexity, speed, and volume of data in 6G can render AI models opaque, turning them into “black boxes” beyond human interpretability [13]. To address this, XAI is essential for revealing model behavior, improving transparency, and reducing false positives and negatives in AI-driven security systems. XAI enhances trust and contributes to more reliable automation in 6G. It also strengthens FL-based systems against poisoning and adversarial attacks [14]. Key XAI techniques, such as Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME) [15], SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [16], and Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) [17] enable model interpretability, while further research may yield methods tailored to B5G/6G demands [13]. Additionally, Large Language Model (LLM)-based agents will play a vital role in explaining and reasoning about IDS and anomaly detection systems through natural language (NL). These agents support automation and transparency in ORAN-based 6G infrastructures [18].

III. EMERGING AI-DRIVEN THREATS AND COUNTERMEASURES

Fig. 2: Threats and Countermeasures for AI in 6G

As AI technologies are expected to be tightly coupled with 6G due to 6G networks being AI-native, the emergence of novel threats related to AI in 6G applications is inevitable. Countermeasures against these threats are vital to achieve the actual benefits of AI-native 6G and 6G applications. This section focuses on two aspects: threats to AI systems and AI-driven threats in 6G. Finally, this section discusses potential countermeasures against such threats, as depicted in Fig. 2.

A. Attacks on AI systems

Data generation in vastly distributed 6G systems calls for decentralized learning techniques such as FL because of their distributed computing and privacy preservation properties. From a 6G network perspective, AI-based intrusion detection [19], AI-based mobility management [20], and AI-enhanced network slicing are 6G functionalities that use FL to train models while keeping the private data local. Moreover, applications such as AI-driven autonomous driving, healthcare, and smart cities will see an increased use of FL for model training. However, adopting FL for model training creates opportunities for data- and model-poisoning attacks in 6G systems [21]. Poisoned models may serve the attacker's purpose and harm 6G functionalities and applications, for example, by classifying malicious network traffic as benign, predicting false handovers, or misallocating resources during network slicing.

Moreover, 6G AI models are vulnerable to attacks in the inference stage if proper security measures are not implemented. These attacks include model evasion attacks, query-based attacks to craft adversarial inputs, and noise-based attacks in which random noise is added to the data to produce incorrect outputs. Owing to the AI-native architecture of the 6G core and the RAN becoming more intelligent and open [22], these attacks will have a significant impact on 6G networks compared to 5G networks. As mentioned in Section II, numerous AI/ML-driven security mechanisms protect 6G and its applications. By successfully launching attacks against AI/ML-based security systems in 6G, attackers can substantially impact the network and make it more vulnerable to additional attacks.

B. Using AI to Attack 6G

Owing to AI's ability to identify patterns in large datasets, adversaries can effectively use AI to learn about 6G and its applications, uncover vulnerabilities using AI techniques, and craft attacks targeting specific vulnerabilities of the 6G system. For example, the massive volume of data generated in the 6G system can be fed to an AI-based traffic analysis system to detect critical traffic and then take action to disrupt it. Generative models can create realistic adversarial inputs to mislead 6G decision-making systems. Intelligent attack scaling is another aspect that can harm 6G systems, as adversaries use AI to maximize the attack impact with minimal effort.

C. Countermeasures

To defend against attacks on AI systems in 6G, defense techniques should be implemented throughout the AI lifecycle, from training to inference. Defence techniques against adversarial attacks can be a potential solution when the model is already deployed in the 6G system. These techniques include adversarial training, where 6G models are trained with adversarial examples [23], and input sanitization, where input data streams are preprocessed to eliminate adversarial perturbations. Novel robust aggregation and differential privacy techniques tailored specifically for 6G use cases can be used as countermeasures against data and model poisoning attacks in 6G. Dynamic resource allocation and AI-powered behavioral analysis can be used to defend against AI-powered DDoS and resource extraction attacks in 6G systems. AI-driven intrusion detection, reinforcement learning-based attack prediction, and mitigation

systems are also effective for real-time threat detection. 6G systems will have sufficient resources for heavy computations on edge networks, especially with concepts such as intelligent RAN. Therefore, resource-intensive methods, such as XAI techniques, can also be used in edge networks [24] for the early detection of attacks in a distributed manner. The model interpretability provided by XAI systems helps analyze the predictions made by AI systems, thus enabling the detection of compromised AI systems. XAI on the 6G edge will prevent attacks from propagating beyond edge networks and provide additional intelligence to the core of other distributed nodes regarding potential attacks. Combining these techniques and developing a unified adaptive secure AI framework will make 6G resilient against adversarial attacks.

IV. GREEN SECURITY FOR SUSTAINABLE 6G

The rise of 6G presents unique opportunities and challenges, particularly in balancing robust security and sustainability. Energy-efficient security techniques are critical for deploying 6G with minimal environmental impact while ensuring high performance and resilience. In this context, energy-efficient security is essential for sustainable 6G deployments. AI offers significant potential to address this need through energy-aware models, dynamic risk assessment, and AI-driven optimization, as shown in Fig. 3.

A. Energy-Aware AI Models

Intelligent AI algorithms enhance security operations by predicting and distributing resources efficiently and optimizing energy consumption for 6G [25]. The ultra-dense and dynamic nature of 6G, with massive connectivity and variable traffic patterns, requires energy-efficient security frameworks that minimize waste by using computational and energy resources only when required. AI-enabled models dynamically adjust the security levels based on energy availability and demand. By incorporating predictive analytics and adaptive resource allocation, these models optimize energy consumption while maintaining high performance and robust security. Energy-aware AI models are essential for efficient security frameworks, aligning with the goals of sustainable and green 6G [26].

B. Dynamic Risk Assessment

Energy-aware AI models aim to minimize energy usage in security operations; however, real-time threats and vulnerabilities in 6G require dynamic adaptability, adding complexity. Dynamic risk assessment addresses this challenge by utilizing AI models trained to respond to security threats and network attacks in real time, while conserving energy. These models analyze network traffic, user behavior, and system characteristics to assess risks and dynamically adjust security controls, such as encryption levels or access permissions, thereby balancing security needs and resource efficiency. A key advantage is the scaling of security measures based on risk levels, reducing measures when risks are low and intensifying them when risks are high, preventing unnecessary energy expenditure and ensuring efficient 6G operations [27]. By exploiting these capabilities, dynamic risk assessment improves 6G security, aligns with sustainability and green communication objectives, and ensures efficient energy usage.

Fig. 3: Key aspects of Green Security for Sustainable 6G

C. AI-Driven Optimization

AI-driven optimization in 6G energy and security can benefit from reinforcement learning to improve resource allocation and management, thereby enabling more efficient energy use in security operations. Given the dynamic nature of 6G, including fluctuations in Channel State Information (CSI), reinforcement learning techniques are particularly effective in defining and adapting security configurations to meet evolving system demands [28]. Recent research emphasizes the potential of hybrid models that combine FL with Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to optimize AI-driven processes for self-sustainable 6G. FL's decentralized framework of FL ensures data privacy, whereas DRL's dynamic decision-making of DRL enhances resource allocation. These hybrid models not only improve energy efficiency but also have applications in optimizing security configurations for 6G systems [29].

Collectively, these techniques integrate green, robust, and adaptive intelligent security mechanisms to ensure sustainability and resilience in 6G communication.

V. LEGAL AND ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The pervasive role of AI in 6G requires robust ethical and legal frameworks, as highlighted in this section.

A. AI Governance for 6G Security

AI governance in 6G is focused on privacy, data protection, security, and transparency. Privacy risks stem from unauthorized access, data leakage, and the misuse of training data. Effective safeguards include advanced cryptographic protocols, blockchain integrated with FL, access controls, identity verification, encryption methods, data anonymization, and pseudonymization. These measures ensure robust privacy protection within the 6G framework [30]. Privacy leakage can be mitigated through techniques such as encoding or reconstructing uploaded information using methods such as semantic

communication and image skeleton generation. Transparent privacy policies that govern data collection, processing, and use, along with explicit consent for data reuse for secondary purposes, help to reduce the risk of misuse, such as profiling. Metrics such as Transparency Comprehension Score and Opt-in Rate for Secondary Users are valuable for evaluating the effectiveness of these measures [30].

AI models face security threats from adversarial model assaults, prompt injections (jailbreak attacks), and poisoning attacks, which undermine the resilience and accuracy of the system, leading to errors. Addressing these risks requires measures such as real-time threat monitoring, regular training data audits, response mechanisms, and vulnerability scanning. Advanced AI/ML techniques, including adversarial training and defensive distillation, are essential for enhancing system security [31]. Key metrics, such as the Penetration Testing Success Rate and Authentication Failure Rate, evaluate a system's resilience to potential threats. In addition to technical measures, non-technical approaches are vital for effective AI governance. Ethical and safe AI operation requires the establishment of ethical guidelines, adherence to legislation, development of comprehensive governance policies, and regular compliance audits. Global collaboration, standardization, codes of conduct, certifications, accountability frameworks, education, training, and public awareness are essential for building trustworthy AI [32].

Transparency in AI requires clear and explainable operations, particularly for unfavorable results. Building trust depends on transparency and explainability, as emphasized by the trustworthy-by-design AI concept. User-friendly interfaces enhance this goal, with metrics such as Explainability Coverage and User Control Interaction Rate providing valuable assessments [30]. Implementing XAI techniques and explainable ML methods improves explainability, enabling users and stakeholders to understand AI behavior and decision-making. Clearly defining the roles and responsibilities of designers, developers, and users ensures accountability for errors and harmful outcomes.

B. Bias Mitigation

There are different types of AI biases, such as algorithm, sampling, representation, conformation, measurement, interaction, and generative bias [33]. The main sources of bias in AI-driven security models are as follows.

Data Bias: Inaccurate, low-quality, or incomplete training data, along with data from biased sources, can lead to unfair outcomes in AI security models. Insufficient representation of demographic groups or characteristics, such as gender, ethnicity, or race, may reinforce social biases. Historical data with embedded prejudices or designers' unintentional biases can further contribute to the unequal treatment of individuals or groups.

Algorithmic Bias: Occurs when biases are introduced during design or implementation, often due to preconceived assumptions or criteria. This can result in unfair outcomes, favoring or disadvantaging certain population groups.

User bias: Occurs when users, consciously or unconsciously, transfer their personal biases during interactions with systems.

Approaches to mitigate bias and ensure fairness during training are categorized into three stages: pre-processing, in-processing, and post-processing, each addressing bias at a specific phase of the training process [33].

- Pre-processing methods aim to detect and mitigate biases and inaccuracies in data before model training. Techniques such as bias augmentation, oversampling, undersampling, adversarial debiasing, data auditing, and cleansing are pivotal. Ensuring bias-aware data collection, high-quality representative training data, diverse design teams, and developer awareness of ethics and fairness can help prevent unfair outcomes and discrimination.
- In the in-processing phase, methods are implemented to reduce bias during training. Continuous monitoring and regular audits help detect imbalances and ensure models maintain fairness throughout implementation.
- In post-processing, auditing and filtering mechanisms address unfair outputs to foster fairness and mitigate bias, balancing trade-offs between bias types. Real-world feedback detects biases during operations. Transparent documentation of model training, testing, and deployment ensures algorithmic transparency, and XAI tools enhance interpretability. Regular updates with new, unbiased data are crucial for maintaining fairness and accuracy.

C. Legal Compliance

Compliance with security and privacy measures, including those related to AI for 6G, is essential to ensure robust and privacy-preserving operation. On the other hand, security and privacy compliance is not vital only for the technical components of the network, including AI, but it is also an enabler for trust among natural persons as end-users. The lack of trust would impact the societal approach towards 6G depending on the erosion of data control. As data volumes scale exponentially across AI-native 6G architectures along with the rapid advancements in AI technologies themselves, the ability of data subjects to exercise meaningful control over the processing of their data diminishes. This could jeopardize digital trust in society. As with security, in terms of trust, AI plays a dual role: it serves as an enabler to restore trust through privacy-preserving techniques such as FL and DP; however, at the same time, AI acts as a factor that multiplies risks. If it is not duly governed, the loss of control would increase as a side effect through pervasive profiling and opaque and ultra-fast autonomous decision-making. Therefore, regulation is necessary for AI-driven security and privacy mechanisms as core network functions to fulfill their potential to ensure that the balance between collective benefit and individual autonomy is sustainable. In this section, an overview of relevant fundamental legislative framework of the EU will be evaluated with the critical highlights of the Digital Omnibus Package. As it is put forward in a critical view of the Digital Omnibus, the protection of fundamental rights, including safety and privacy, should not be sacrificed in the pursuit of speed and political convenience in any regulatory attempt [34].

AI Act: AI Act compliance begins with identifying the risk category. According to the AI Act Article 6(2) along with

Annex III, AI systems as critical digital infrastructure in 6G network would be classified as high-risk AI. This triggers a full cascade of requirements for high-risk AI (risk management, data governance, cybersecurity, etc.). Article 15/5 is a crucial provision for 6G AI security, explicitly mandating the prevention of specific attack categories that 6G AI systems would face, including data poisoning, model poisoning, and adversarial examples. Under this legislative framework, AI regulatory sandboxes could serve as a tolerance layer for 6G security and privacy preparedness. The EU regulator foresaw the need for testing AI systems under supervised environments; accordingly, the AI Act enables regulatory sandboxes as controlled environments, which are critical for developing AI to strengthen the security and privacy of the network without imposing premature compliance burdens. In 2025, the General Purpose AI (GPAI) Code of Practice was published in the EU as a voluntary tool for providers of GPAI models for AI Act compliance, including a safety and security chapter. In a highly heterogeneous network such as 6G, a collaborative approach is essential to ensure security; therefore, in the GPAI, the signatories are expected to commit to strengthening the knowledge base of AI incidents by tracking and documenting.

GDPR: The EU's GDPR is crucial for protecting personal data, particularly in 6G use cases, where data processing will be highly automated, and data processing will be real-time. Emerging privacy threats and misuse of collected data will raise significant concerns that have not been observed today [35]. According to the GDPR 35, 6G networks performing real-time user profiling for resource optimization would necessitate data protection impact assessments. This is because AI for 6G security constitutes a systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects based on automated data processing. In the sense of AI Related technical regulatory mandates, the GDPR involves data protection by design and by default (Art. 25). Rather than being merely engineering choices, FL, DP in training data, and on-device inference are also legal compliance strategies in the sense of GDPR. However, some provisions of the GDPR also would serve to strengthen security to provide data protection. For example, Article 32/1 stipulates the importance of SoTA security in data processing. For 6G networks, the "state of the art" could be interpreted to involve adversarial robustness techniques and promote AI as an enabler for security.

NIS2 Directive: According to NIS2 Article 2, telecommunications and digital infrastructure providers are "essential entities." AI in 6G networks is not merely software running on infrastructure; it simultaneously constitutes the infrastructure itself. NIS2 underscores ten minimum security measures, including risk analysis, incident handling, business continuity, supply chain security, vulnerability disclosure, cryptography policies, multi-factor authentication, and secured emergency communication systems (NIS2 Article 21/2). One of the potential gaps in NIS2 regarding AI security in 6G is the incident notification requirement within 24 hours (Article 23). Considering the ultralow-latency structure of 6G, adversarial attacks on 6G AI models might compromise network integrity in milliseconds, which would be a legal and compliance challenge for NIS2.

Cyber Resilience Directive (CRA): According to CRA,

products with digital elements must be designed with no known exploitable vulnerabilities and must receive security updates throughout their entire life cycle. Accordingly, newly discovered adversarial techniques must be patched for 6G AI software. Under the CRA, 6G network equipment with embedded AI could be classified as “important” or “critical” products requiring third-party conformity assessment because they involve critical cybersecurity functions (Article 6 and Annex III).

Digital Networks Act (DNA): Proposing DNA on 21 January 2026, the EU Legislator aims to unify the telecommunication and spectrum rules for modernizing next generation network connectivity legal framework. The DNA will replace the European Electronic Communication Code and aims to create a simple and harmonized EU legal framework to accelerate innovation and investment in resilient and advanced AI, cloud, and space infrastructure for communication networks. The DNA proposal treats AI itself as an attack surface. However, it is worth noting also the critics for the DNA implying that the mandatory fair share provisions of this proposal would undermine the net-neutrality principle and create a fragmented internet [36]. The net neutrality debate in the DNA is highly valuable because it is directly related to AI-enabled security and privacy in 6G networks. Without robust open-internet safeguards, telecom operators can throttle or differentially treat real-time AI-driven security functions in 6G [37].

Digital Omnibus Package: The EU Commission adopted its Digital Omnibus Package (2025/0360) on November 19, 2025. It aims to address compliance challenges arising from situations covered by different legislative instruments on data protection, AI, and cybersecurity. For example, data rules will be consolidated under two major pieces of legislation: the Data Act and the GDPR. Regarding data protection and privacy, this package also aims to narrow down the definition of personal data: if a data controller is unable to identify a natural person by using the obtained data with the means available, such data will not fall within the scope of the GDPR. Considering that 6G technology is fundamentally data-driven, it may be argued that, under this provision, certain types of nonpersonal data obtained from the network would not fall within the scope of the GDPR. However, a key point to be considered is that the AI systems integrated into the network must not be capable of identifying a natural person by using this certain type of data. One of the 6G-aligned amendments proposed in the Digital Omnibus is to create a single entry point for all cybersecurity incidents and data breach reports in compliance with EU cybersecurity legislation.

VI. ROLE OF LLMs IN NEXT GENERATION IDS

GAI, particularly LLMs, has emerged as a promising direction for IDS. Following the success of recent LLMs, research has increasingly examined their applicability beyond conversational tasks. This study investigates the feasibility of applying LLMs to network IDS using the widely used benchmark dataset CIC-IDS2017 [38]. Following data preprocessing, a few-shot prompting pipeline performs binary classification of traffic as *benign* or *malicious*. The motivation is to assess whether LLMs can generalize their pretrained knowledge for intrusion detection tasks with minimal labeled data and without resource-intensive fine-tuning.

A. Dataset Preparation

The CIC-IDS2017 dataset was selected because of its diverse attack classes and extensive use in ML-based IDS research, despite not originating from a 5G edge environment. To manage the LLM inference costs, a balanced subset of 10,060 samples was constructed with equal numbers of benign and malicious instances. Data cleaning addressed inconsistencies in column names and removed duplicates, infinite, and null values. Attack data were organized by consolidating sub-attack types into primary classes, including Brute Force, DoS/D-DoS, Web, Infiltration, Botnet, and Port Scan. Approximately 1,000 samples were drawn from each attack class, except for infiltration, which was limited by availability. These were combined with an equal number of benign samples to create a representative dataset suitable for binary classification.

B. LLM-Assisted IDS

The proposed LLM-assisted IDS was evaluated using three distinct and well-established LLMs to ensure model diversity, as shown in Table I. To reduce the inference cost, the token usage per API call was minimized through feature reduction. Constant features were removed, followed by the mutual information-based selection of the 20 most informative features from the remaining set. Prior to inference, all attack types were merged into a single malicious category, and the task was framed as a binary classification problem for simplicity in analysis. This streamlined representation enables an efficient evaluation of the LLM performance in intrusion detection. Furthermore, owing to differences in the supported context window sizes among the selected LLMs, the batch size for Mistral Small 3.2 was reduced to ensure stable execution. The temperature parameter was fixed at 0.1 to encourage deterministic outputs [39].

TABLE I: Built-In and Experiment Parameters of Used LLMs

LLM	Built in Attributes			Experiment Configurations		
	Parameters (in Billions)	Context Window (Tokens)	Cost (USD)	Temperature	Max tokens	Batch Size
Gemini 2.5 Flash Lite	Not Officially Disclosed	1.05M	0.10/M input tokens 0.40/M output tokens	0.1	4096	25
Llama 4 Maverick	17	1.05M	0.15/M input tokens 0.60/M output tokens			25
Mistral Small 3.2	24	131K	0.06/M input tokens 0.18/M output tokens			15

This evaluation did not rely on LLM fine-tuning; instead, a few-shot prompting strategy was used for classification. For each API request, the LLM was provided with seven representative examples from each attack class, including benign traffic. These examples were structured using a reusable prompt format, referred to as the “Few-Shot Prompting Template,” below serving as an example for few-shot prompting. Because LLMs are not natively designed for tabular data, the input samples were converted into a sentence-based format using the template. The content in this prompting template was provided to the API as a “System Prompt” to define the system’s role, while batches of test samples were supplied as “User Prompts” to obtain binary predictions of `BENIGN` or `MALICIOUS`.

Finally, 1,006 test samples were evaluated in batches during inference. The results were averaged over three experimental runs and are reported in Table II. Because some LLM outputs required post-processing to address null or infinite values, the

effective test set size varied between approximately ~ 950 and 1,006 samples across the runs. The performance of the LLM-based approaches was compared with three conventional ML baselines using the same 20 features selected via mutual-information-based feature selection, with ML models trained on 9,054 labeled benign and malicious samples. As reported in Table II, traditional ML methods outperformed LLM-based approaches across all evaluation metrics. Among the ML baselines, XGBoost and Random Forests consistently achieved the strongest performance, whereas Logistic Regression showed results comparable to the LLMs. In addition, the ML models demonstrated greater stability than the LLMs in the three experimental runs.

```
> Few Shot Prompting Template
=====
You are a Network Intrusion Detection
System (IDS). Your task is to classify
network traffic flows as 'BENIGN' or
'MALICIOUS'.
Here are examples of how you should
analyze the data:
---
Example: 1
Input: {"Destination Port": 53,
"Init_Win_bytes_backward": -1, "Packet
Length Mean": 43.2, ...}
Output: {'classifications': [{'id': 8159,
'label': 'BENIGN'}]}
Example: 2
...
Example: 7
Input: {"Destination Port": 80,
"Init_Win_bytes_backward": 28960, "Packet
Length Mean": 0, ...}
Output: {'classifications': [{'id': 2731,
'label': 'MALICIOUS'}]}
---
I will provide traffic logs with 20
features each. Analyze the combination of
these features to detect anomalies.
OUTPUT FORMAT:
You must return a JSON Object strictly
following this schema:
{"classifications": [{"id": <input_id>,
"label": "BENIGN" or "MALICIOUS"}, ...]}
IMPORTANT: The 'id' in your output MUST
match the 'id' provided in the input
record.
CRITICAL: You MUST provide exactly one
classification for EVERY single record in
the batch. Do not skip any.
```

Although LLMs exhibited lower overall performance, they demonstrated a relatively strong ability to detect attack traffic (higher recall), which is a critical requirement in an IDS to minimize false negatives. However, their effectiveness in identifying normal traffic is limited. In addition to detection performance, LLMs offer additional value through their NL-driven capability to describe and contextualize detected attacks. Although existing XAI techniques for tabular data, such as LIME and SHAP, provide useful insights, more expressive approaches are required for advanced scenarios, including zero-

TABLE II: Binary Class Intrusion Detection Performance for LLM and ML Models

		Train Accuracy	Test Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	AUC
LLM Models	Gemini 2.5 Flash Lite	-	0.57	0.55	0.89	0.68	0.57
	Llama 4 Maverick	-	0.72	0.65	0.95	0.77	0.72
	Mistral Small 3.2	-	0.65	0.59	0.99	0.74	0.66
ML Models	Logistic Regression	0.85	0.85	0.82	0.89	0.85	0.89
	XGBoost	1.00	0.99	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Random Forest	1.00	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	1.00

day attacks [40]. In this context, LLMs represent a promising approach for enhancing IDS explainability. Nevertheless, challenges such as hallucinations [41] remain, and future work may address these issues through LLM fine-tuning or by integrating additional contextual knowledge using techniques such as Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) [42].

VI CONCLUSION

The evolution of 6G and the adoption of AI/ML present both opportunities and challenges for securing and protecting privacy in next-generation communication infrastructures. Therefore, innovative security solutions and privacy protection mechanisms that integrate advanced technologies and align with regulatory frameworks and ethical principles are required. This survey highlights SoTA techniques and key enablers and identifies areas requiring further research to ensure secure and sustainable AI-powered 6G infrastructure and services.

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